

CURRENT ASPECTS OF TRANSIENT ISCHAEMIC ATTACK

Rizvonov Jasur Qurbonovich, Avazova Nilufar Baxtiyorovna, Amonov SHERZOD Bahodir o'g'li
Karshi State University

Abstract: The article presents the modern strategy of diagnosis and treatment of patients with transient ischaemic attacks (TIA). The issues of terminology and new definition of TIA are discussed. The results of studies proving the effectiveness of early aggressive treatment, including angioplasty, in preventing the development of irreversible brain damage in patients with TIA are reviewed.

Key words: fluoroquinolones, moxifloxacin, antibacterial activity.

Introduction. Approximately 15 million people develop stroke worldwide each year, of whom more than 5 million die and about 5 million more are permanently dependent on care [1,15]. There are no accurate data on the prevalence of transient ischaemic attacks (TIAs) in most countries. Some estimates suggest that up to 5 million adults in the USA suffer them each year, with many TIAs remaining undiagnosed [2]. Numerous cohort studies in the United States and other countries around the world have demonstrated a varying incidence of TIA, ranging from 0.37 to 1.1 per 1000 persons per year. Similar to stroke, the risk of TIA increases significantly with age. According to the Cardiovascular Health Study (1993), the prevalence of TIA was 2.7% in men 65-69 years of age and 1.6% in women of the same age, and it increased to 3.6% and 4.1% in men and women 75-79 years of age, respectively. In a British study [3], the incidence of TIA among persons over 85 years of age reached 6.41 per 1000. At the same time, in stroke survivors, TIAs in the history are noted in quite a significant number of cases - from 7 to 40%. It is believed that such a large variation is explained by a number of factors, including different criteria for diagnosing TIA in different studies. TIA as an episode of sudden onset and short-term neurological deficit has long been considered a 'benign' pathology. Unfortunately, many patients and general practitioners still do not sufficiently understand the nature and significance of TIA. It has now been proven that TIA is as urgent a pathological condition as ischaemic stroke. The basis of both conditions is ischaemia due to a mismatch between the blood supply needs of the brain and the actual blood flow. It is the unity of pathogenesis that explains the high risk of recurrence of cerebral circulatory failure after TIA. It is shown that from 10 to 15% of all persons with TIA within 3 months suffer a stroke, and from a quarter to half of this number of patients - in the first 48 h after TIA. At the same time, once a stroke has developed, the risk of recurrent stroke in the first 3 months is approximately 4-8%. In addition, TIA also increases the risk of other cardiovascular complications, including myocardial infarction, as well as vascular death. Taking into account the prognosis of patients after TIA, experts of the European Stroke Organisation (ESO) have significantly revised the management of such patients. TIA is considered as one of the most important independent risk factors for ischaemic stroke and death, especially in the first months [4,16].

Since the 1960s, the definition of TIA has been traditionally used in clinical practice, with time as the main criterion for distinguishing it from ischaemic stroke. TIA was considered as a sudden onset neurological deficit, presumably of vascular origin, lasting no more than 24 hours. This '24-hour rule' was also reflected in the 1988 World Health Organisation (WHO) definition, according to which the diagnosis of TIA was to be established in case of rapidly developing clinical symptoms of focal or diffuse brain damage occurring without obvious extravascular causes and lasting less than 24 hours. In 2002, G.W. Albers et al. proposed to modify this definition so that the focus of attention shifted from the criteria of time of symptom development and resolution to the fact of formation of pathological ischaemic changes in brain tissue: 'TIA is a short-term episode of neurological dysfunction due to focal cerebral or retinal ischaemia, manifesting clinical symptoms usually for less than 1 h and without signs of cerebral infarction'[5,17]. The premise of the new interpretation is that current evidence suggests that in the majority of patients with TIA (at least 60%), symptoms resolve within the first

hour and very rarely continue for up to 24 hours. Only 14% of patients with TIA resolve symptoms after 6 h or more. In less than 1 in 6 patients in whom symptoms of cerebral ischaemia persist for more than 1 h, they disappear within 24 h.[6,18]. Moreover, in the vast majority of patients in such a case, neuroimaging reveals signs of cerebral infarction. Therefore, the new definition was welcomed by many specialists and managed to enter into practice, as well as used in a universal antihypoxant and antioxidant used in the complex therapy of various neurological and metabolic diseases, as well as their complications

- Metabolic and vascular diseases of the brain (stroke, traumatic brain injury, encephalopathies of various genesis):

1000-2000 mg intravenous drip 10-14 days, then 400-800 mg intravenously (up to 5 ml v/m) 10 days, then 1-2 tablets 3 times a day, at least 4-6 weeks

- Peripheral vascular, metabolic disorders and their consequences, including diabetic polyneuropathy:

400-2000 mg intravenous drip (up to 5 ml v/m) 10-20 days, then 1-2 tablets 3 times a day, at least 4-6 weeks

- Wound healing (trophic ulcers, diabetic foot syndrome, pressure sores, frostbite):

800-2000 mg intravenous drip (up to 5 ml v/m) 10-20 days, then 1-2 tablets 3 times a day, at least 4-6 weeks Doses depend on the severity and severity of symptoms of the disease a number of large clinical trials.

It should be noted that to date, no convincing evidence has been obtained to confirm the rationality of using certain time criteria for the diagnosis of TIA. According to S.C. Jonston et al. [2,19], TIA symptomatology lasting more than even 10 min is a significant risk factor for stroke development in the next hours. In any case, the key criterion differentiating TIA from stroke is the presence of infarct changes in the ischemic zone, and they do not always correlate with the severity, duration, and persistence of symptoms. Neuroimaging methods of examination make it possible to detect brain infarction in many situations when TIA is suspected on the basis of clinical symptoms. According to the AHA/ASA, this error occurs in 30-50% of all cases of TIA diagnosis according to the criteria of the 'old' definition. Therefore, many experts suggest that the time criterion should not be used in the definition of TIA at all, and attention should be paid only to the features of tissue damage - transient ischaemia without infarction development [7].

The rationale for this opinion is that, in fact, the only significant difference between TIA and stroke is the development of infarction - irreversible damage to brain tissue or retina. It is irrational to use the '24-hour rule', as well as the indication of the typical disappearance of TIA symptoms within 1 hour, in routine practice - patients with cerebral or retinal circulatory disorders should be examined and treated according to the unified algorithm of acute cerebrovascular disorders, regardless of how long ago these disorders occurred. Moreover, the earlier diagnosis and treatment start, the better prognosis both in stroke and TIA.

Currently, in clinical practice, 'classical' and 'new' definitions of TIA are used. The classical definition of TIA is based on a time interval of neurological symptom persistence of no more than 24 hours, which is chosen for ease of application, primarily for epidemiological purposes. The new definition of TIA, given the lack of reliable clinical methods to distinguish between reversible and irreversible cerebral ischaemia, gives priority to imaging of organic brain changes as opposed to the criterion of time. In other words, only objective confirmation of the presence or absence of infarct changes in brain tissue or retina provides a basis for timely and clear differentiation between TIA and stroke (similar to the differentiation between angina pectoris and myocardial infarction). This is essential both for the correct treatment of stroke in the shortest possible time and for the active prevention of stroke in the case of TIA. A transient cerebral or retinal circulatory disturbance is virtually the same cerebrovascular accident as a stroke, with equally unfavourable consequences,

reflecting the severity of which is a high early risk of stroke and death. However, the new definition of TIA has certain drawbacks and remains the subject of ongoing debate [7,20]. Firstly, its implementation requires equipping the hospital with diagnostic equipment and therefore cannot be fully utilised in many regions, primarily in developing countries of the world. In addition, in adopting the new definition of TIA, specialists should realise that from now on, the results of many clinical trials in which TIA and stroke were diagnosed according to the previous criteria will be incomparable (at least directly) with the new evidence base. This will significantly limit the ability to compare the results of old and new studies, and in some cases will make it impossible to conduct meta-analyses and systematic reviews without accumulating a large amount of new evidence. Nevertheless, this should not in itself be an obstacle to the introduction of a new definition of TIA, as the revision of terminology will help to improve diagnostic accuracy, which is much more important for modern medicine. However, in some situations, even neuroimaging examination cannot detect a brain infarction (especially if it is small) and correctly distinguish between TIA and stroke. In such cases, the time factor will indeed play a decisive role in the diagnosis of stroke. But for the majority of patients, the definition of TIA based on visualisation of ischaemic cerebral changes, i.e. objective evidence of the presence or absence of infarction, will be the optimal decision in the choice of the subsequent management strategy.

Because of the high risk of stroke, patients with TIA should receive the same urgent diagnostic and therapeutic care as in the case of stroke. The effectiveness of active prevention of cerebrovascular accident is particularly high if timely measures are taken in the first hours and day after TIA.

According to the new AHA/ASA strategy (2009), all patients with TIA should undergo neuroimaging examination within the first 24 h from the onset of symptoms [7,22]. In accordance with this requirement, all individuals who have had a TIA at least 72 h ago should be admitted to an acute cerebrovascular accident unit, given the high risk of stroke in the next few hours.

Another rationale for hospitalisation of patients with TIA is the need for neuroimaging. Visualising methods of examination allow:

- 1) confirm the presence or absence of irreversible changes in brain tissue (brain infarction);
- 2) exclude non-ischaemic causes of the disease;
- 3) determine the mechanism of ischaemia development (large vessel atherothrombosis, cardioembolism, lacunar lesion of small arteries) and accordingly choose the most rational treatment tactics;
- 4) assess the degree of risk and prognosis. Neuroimaging is the preferred neuroimaging method experts consider magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) for TIA diagnosis and differential diagnosis with stroke, especially in diffusion-weighted mode, which provides the most accurate early assessment of ischaemic brain damage. If MRI is not available, X-ray computed tomography is recommended.

Noninvasive (mainly ultrasound) visualisation of neck vessels and preferably intracranial vessels is an obligatory component of diagnostics of a patient with TIA. This will allow to clarify the mechanism of cerebral ischaemia development and, in case of occlusive carotid lesion detection, to perform surgical intervention, the prophylactic efficacy of which is the highest in the first weeks after TIA. In addition, electrocardiography should be performed as soon as possible. If a cardiogenic cause of cerebral circulatory failure is suspected, echocardiography should be performed - at least transthoracic, if possible also transesophageal. In case of unknown origin of ischaemia, especially in elderly people, Holter monitoring is necessary to verify paroxysmal atrial fibrillation. Blood tests are also mandatory: general and biochemical analysis, coagulogram, lipid profile. This will help to exclude conditions that can mimic TIA (e.g., hypoglycaemia), or diagnose a blood disease - the cause of intravascular thrombosis (e.g., true polycythemia). In addition, clarification of the presence and severity of the most important cardiovascular risk factors (including dyslipidaemia, hyperglycaemia) is necessary for rational stroke prevention.

The aim of treatment of patients with TIA is to prevent subsequent TIA and ischaemic stroke. Treatment consists of correction of the pathology that caused the TIA and control of modifiable risk factors (arterial hypertension, diabetes mellitus, smoking, dyslipidaemia, cardiac disorders). Patients with severe (70% or more) carotid atherosclerotic stenosis should be referred to a vascular surgeon for carotid endarterectomy. The reduction in the absolute five-year cumulative risk of stroke or death after performing carotid endarterectomy in the first week after TIA compared with conservative therapy is maximum at 18.5% [8]. Delayed performance of the operation between 4 and 12 weeks and after 12 weeks significantly reduces the effectiveness of the intervention to the level of absolute risk values of 5.5% and 0.8%, respectively. Anticoagulants are the drugs of choice among antithrombotic agents in atrial fibrillation, both permanent and paroxysmal forms, acute coronary syndrome with ST-segment elevation, mitral stenosis, prosthetic heart valves. For faster results, therapy can be started with direct anticoagulants with a switch to vitamin K antagonists (warfarin). In patients with noncardioembolic stroke the drugs of choice are platelet antiplatelet antiaggregants - acetylsalicylic acid (ASA), clopidogrel, ticlopidine, slow-release dipyridamole (SRD) in combination with ASA. More The results of the prospective EXPRESS trial [9] are in favour of immediate 'aggressive' combined treatment of patients with TIA. The study started in the early 2000s and consisted of two phases. In phase 1, 307 patients with TIA or small stroke admitted to the clinic 3 (interquartile range 2-5) days after the development of neurological symptoms were examined during 30 months. All patients received antithrombotic therapy. Antiplatelet therapy during the 1st month consisted in the administration of ASC (300 mg loading dose, further 75 mg/day) and clopidogrel (300 mg loading dose, further 75 mg/day) at high risk of stroke according to the AVSE scale [10]. Subsequently, dipyridamole MB 400 mg plus ASC 50 mg/day was recommended. 62% of patients were prescribed antihypertensive therapy (perindopril 4 mg combined with in-dapamide 1.25 mg), 65% - statins (simvastatin 40 mg). In the first 30 days from the onset of cerebral impairment, only 2 (12%) of 17 patients underwent carotid endarterectomy. In the subsequent 90 days of follow-up, cases of recurrent cerebral circulation disorders, myocardial infarction or death were recorded.

After completion of phase 1, phase 2 of the study was initiated, during which an additional 280 patients with TIA or small stroke were also included for 30 months. The main difference in phase 2 was immediate hospitalisation after 1 (0-3) day ($p < 0.0001$ compared to phase 1) and earlier administration of antithrombotic, hypo-lipidaemic and antihypertensive therapy ($p < 0.0001$ compared to phase 1). The same agents remained the drugs of choice, but the number of patients treated with antihypertensive and hypolipidaemic therapy was significantly higher. Carotid endarterectomy was performed in 10 (67%) of 15 patients within the first 30 days from the onset of cerebral dysfunction, with intervention performed in 6 (40%) patients within the first 6 days. Further follow-up was carried out according to the same scheme. Comparative analysis showed that the risk of first and recurrent stroke was significantly higher in patients in phase 1 of the study and was 10.3% versus 2.1% for phase 2 of the study ($p < 0.0001$). The cumulative risk of non-fatal stroke, myocardial infarction or death was also significantly higher in phase 1 compared to phase 2 (11.9% vs 3.6%, $p = 0.0002$) [9]. The presented results convincingly demonstrate that urgent examination, immediate initiation of comprehensive conservative therapy, and prompt surgical intervention can reduce the risk of early recurrent stroke after TIA or minor stroke by 80% and halve the total number of recurrent strokes.

The treatment strategy for ischaemic stroke, in addition to reperfusion aimed at restoring blood flow in the ischaemic focus, also includes the implementation of neuroprotection, the main goal of which is to maintain the viability of brain tissue for the subsequent restoration of impaired cerebral functions. The theoretical prerequisite for the use of various cytoprotectors is the established sequence of pathological events (the so-called 'ischaemic cascade'), which results in the development of irreversible damage - brain infarction [11]. On the other hand, reperfusion cerebral changes, i.e. occurring under conditions of restored blood flow, involve the same mechanisms. In other words, even in the case of spontaneous restoration of blood flow, which is observed in TIA, neuronal loss is a real problem. Clinical evidence of such a situation can be found in the development of diffuse neurological symptoms in patients with 'stroke-free' course of chronic cerebrovascular disease, in whose anamnesis one can find indications of

short-term episodes of disturbances of sensitivity, coordination, speech slurring, etc. In this connection, the issues of cytoprotectors use in TIA become urgent, and the most promising are agents capable of blocking both the earliest and delayed reactions leading to neuronal death.

One of the main mechanisms of cell damage is oxidative stress. Ischaemia has a damaging effect on antioxidant systems, leading to the formation of reactive oxygen species. These processes initiate glutamate excitotoxicity, accumulation of calcium ions, necrosis and apoptosis of brain cells [11, 12]. Oxidative stress is realised both in conditions of oxygen deficiency and excess and develops already in the first hours of ischemia, and spontaneous or induced reperfusion causes the second wave of cerebral damage. That is why antioxidants and antihypoxants remain the most demanded agents with neuroprotective properties in the existing clinical practice. Another promising direction is the development of drugs that normalise mitochondrial functions and energy supply. In other words, even in the case of spontaneous restoration of blood flow, which is observed in TIA, neuronal loss is a real problem. Clinical evidence of such a situation can be found in the development of diffuse neurological symptoms in patients with 'stroke-free' course of chronic cerebrovascular disease, in whose anamnesis one can find indications of short-term episodes of disturbances of sensitivity, coordination, speech slurring, etc. In this connection, the issues of cytoprotectors use in TIA become urgent, and the most promising are agents capable of blocking both the earliest and delayed reactions leading to neuronal death.

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Conclusions: Thus, TIA is an urgent condition that is a marker of high risk of early stroke. The reversibility of TIA disorders provides an opportunity to diagnose the cause of acute cerebral circulatory failure and prevent the development of severe organic brain changes. The main principles of medical tactics in TIA are emergency hospitalisation and examination of the patient, multicomponent conservative therapy using antithrombotic, antihypertensive, hypolipidemic drugs and antioxidants. If carotid endarterectomy is indicated, the operation should be performed as early as possible - within the first week after TIA. Emergency tactics can really reduce the risk of stroke, prevent death or disability of the patient, and this chance should be maximally used.

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